

School culture and the quality of learning: The experience in Special Region of Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT

Structural-based education is a significant challenge for elements of education in Indonesia. However, in the province of the Special Region of Yogyakarta, an alternative cultural approach strategy is applied during challenges from the structural model. This research uses the ethnographic method. The results showed that the quality of learning in research was based on structural learning strategies and value-based development efforts, which were then applied and applied in a learning culture (behavior, knowledge, and artefacts). These efforts are combined into a pattern of developing a learning culture and the pattern of gradual change, which also becomes a study. This research aims to bring up the concept of developing cultural learning strategies through values and practices while implementing structural educational policies. This study has limitations in the form of gaps in structural education problems that have not been confirmed, which are more inclined to the policy and political context, so the study requires a study pattern with a broader scope related to structural education problems that are still difficult to resolve, such as the development of equal access policies, education, and corruption.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of secondary education in Indonesia was not promising enough to support future human resources progress. This condition refers to data from the Program for International Student Assessment-Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development or PISA-OECD study [1], which states that more than 50% of secondary education graduates in Indonesia with achievement quality 3 years behind the average secondary education index of the surveyed countries [1]. In addition, a report published by the world bank states that structural efforts in the form of decentralization and reform of gender equality in the education system in Indonesia are still facing challenges in the form of the lack of students' ability to pass national standardized exams for secondary level education, 70% of students who have not been able to demonstrate literacy through the PISA-2018 indicators. Students are left behind in areas with poor socio-economic conditions [2]. The data shows that at the same level in secondary education, the ability of secondary education graduates in Indonesia has not been achieved optimally, at least from the minimum ability set or showing contextual advantages according to the expertise possessed.

Several studies have argued that the portrait of education in Indonesia is still unable to produce superior quality graduates due to the structural development model of education in Indonesia. These factors include poor structural system development at the level of policy organizers [3], education has not had a substantial impact in increasing learning output and there are still gaps in access to education between regions [4], expansion of access to education which is constrained by political agendas, limited budget, mechanism, and lack of appreciation of awards [5], quality gaps between schools and the lack of policies to improve the quality of education facilitation [6], [7], calculation of poor budgeting scores up to not comparable to improving the quality of education [8], the mechanism for measuring teacher performance improvements related to student output is not significant [9], not yet optimal contextuality of curriculum implementation in schools [10], quality constraints and implementer commitment technical staff (teachers), education administrators, and poor parental participation [11], to corruption which has a negative impact on education sector spending in several regions in Indonesia [12]. The various factors behind the poor portrait of education in Indonesia mainly arise from the structural model, which is the result of the policy formulation of the organizers in the education sector. The structural model formulated contextually is continued technically by the implementers in the field to produce the quality of student output with a quality that is not yet optimal.

The factors that make the poor portrait of education in Indonesia are structural patterns currently facing obstacles and challenges in implementing the education system. So, in this context, alternative options are needed in achieving the goal of producing different quality outputs for students and overcoming the problem of insignificant quality of secondary education graduates based on the results of observations of PISA-OECD [1] and a summary of the quality of education in Indonesia according to the executive summary of the World Bank report [2]. The Indonesian Directorate of High School Development of the Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbud) has attempted to implement structural quality improvements in the form of regulations, engineering linearity of information delivery systems with demands, curriculum changes and governance, training and technical guidance for organizers and administrators. Technical implementer. Based on the facts studied practically and theoretically, many failures and ineffectiveness appear when the structural paradigm is continuously built and continued in a format that tends to be the same. Especially concerning efforts to increase education capacity in the long term, which requires concepts, contextuality, and explicit support from various parties (government, schools, and the community).

In 2003, developments were carried out in the form of implementing cultural strategies to improve the quality of education in Indonesia [13], but unfortunately, in Indonesia, there are not many studies that discuss the implementation of cultural strategies in depth. This application is mainly in the aspect of the level of effectiveness and the impact of its application in schools so that it attracts researchers to study more deeply regarding the chances of success of the strategy through several determined study areas. Experiences of successful implementation of cultural strategies applied by several countries, such as the achievement in Australia with an emphasis on four approaches, namely the product approach, the facilitated product approach, the network of facilitator approach, and the thematic approach (webbed network); which then results in cultural changes, especially in the participatory roles and capacities of students [14].

In Finland, cultural change in the education system centered on the role of teachers in facilitating the improvement of the quality of students and involving parents as part of education, as well as using the keywords pedagogical orientation and critical freedom of students and then there is an ongoing educational transformation [15]–[17], thus forming an inclusive learning pattern [18], and in Singapore which is a country with the best academic reputation in Southeast Asia, applies a pattern of cultural education in order to overcome the dynamics of inequality by multi-ethnic and structural education challenges through the application of cooperative learning strategies and a comfortable learning environment with implications for critical teaching, teacher capacity building, to encourage the active role of students [19]–[21]. Another argument is that in Singapore, the emphasis lies on developing curriculum innovation and teacher capacity concerning the diffusion of patterns of adaptability of teacher expertise [22]. Lee and Hung [22] use several strategies to increase teacher adaptability, including managerial Leadership that opens up opportunities for teacher innovation and builds learning experiment efforts, pedagogical-based learning, building teacher networks for capacity building, and historical-based learning of teacher adaptability patterns. [22]. From experience, Indonesia has similarities in terms of the need to increase the capacity of educators, the multi-ethnic presence of students, to the structural challenges that are difficult to overcome in the education sector.

The design of early education development through a cultural approach was formulated by Spradley [23], who suggested that three cultures must be developed in advancing schools, including a culture of behavior (behavior culture), culture of knowledge (knowledge culture), and culture of artefacts (artefacts culture). Individually, this implementation takes the form of a positive culture in schools in shaping the behavior of school members related to religiosity, discipline, responsibility, the rationality of thinking and solving problems, learning motivation, problem-solving habits rationally, discussion/collaboration, and belief in oneself and others. Students must have good relations with school members, respect for friends, openness, togetherness, the spirit of life, honesty, unity and oneness. Either individually or collectively, both will have

an impact on the progress and quality of schools, given the orientation of human factors, values and beliefs to the acceptance of the existence of multicultural situations [24].

The development of education based on a cultural approach strategy is practiced in secondary schools (SMA) in the province of the Special Region of Yogyakarta, including SMAN 1 Yogyakarta, SMAN 2 Yogyakarta, and SMAN 3 Yogyakarta. The students are encouraged to implement learning models after formal learning activities completed and there is a pattern of interaction in the form of repetition of previous learning before formal learning activities begin. Both are carried out independently and voluntarily without any obligation to participate. However, there is a high form of participation from students in a conducive manner, and it is supported by the capacity of technical implementers, namely teachers and staff, who continuously support these conditions so that their reputations continue to survive. A conducive learning system is characterized by the agreement of school residents in achieving goals, the learning process and continuous quality improvement; teachers and school staff are responsible for the learning process, a social and collaborative atmosphere, and supported by increased professionalism [25]. The cultural approach strategy shows a significant influence in improving the quality of schools through positive development. In the description that has been explained, the researcher found that there were advantages of the cultural approach strategy that had been built so that researchers were more interested in knowing the development culture in the two schools and how the development techniques were used.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Qualitative research uses a naturalistic approach concerning Spradley [23]. The naturalistic approach is used in describing and analyzing school culture in the form of behavior, knowledge, and artefacts culture until seeing verbal messages and values contained. Observations, documentation and interviews were conducted at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta, SMAN 2 Yogyakarta, and SMAN 3 Yogyakarta by taking field data in the form of: i) Knowledge and behavior from school principals, teachers, students and administrative staff; ii) Artefacts in the form of documents, achievements, and objects; iii) Verbal messages in the form of school rules/regulations and programs, and; iv) The values contained in the culture of behavior, artefacts, and verbal messages. The research procedure uses four stages of activity in the form of setting selection, data collection, fulfilment of credibility, and data analysis.

In the data collection phase, informants are determined based on the presence of full enculturation in the research area, direct involvement with the object of research, willingness in terms of time to achieve natural research results, and good behavior from informants. The data was taken in the form of qualitative data about the culture of behavior, culture of knowledge, culture of artefacts, verbal messages, and data values through observation, interviews, questionnaires, and documentation. Observations are in the form of observing four things: i) In the form of patterns of discipline enforcement, technical capabilities, strategies, structures, policies, and delivery of information by school principals; ii) From teacher behavior in the form of discipline enforcement, application of learning methods and media, administrative activities, participation in self-development, to discussion/collaboration in their network; iii) Observation on students by looking at ethics and attitudes, discipline, peer discussion/collaboration, presentation capacity, learning culture, and the ability to imagine in writing articles; and iv) Observation on organizational behavior related to discipline enforcement, service, discussion/collaboration, participation in self-development.

In observing the culture of artefacts, researchers took documents of national exam scores, school and student awards, school capacity in facilitating students' academic/non-academic achievements, and capacity to maintain school physical assets. Verbal messages are represented through the development of verbal messages in the form of student, teacher, and administrative staff rules that are applied in schools which are then measured how the pattern of compliance from all elements of the school is measured. In value observation, the researcher observes how students develop and implement the values contained in the culture of behavior, artefacts, and verbal messages. In-depth interviews were conducted with the criteria of natural, informal, without psychological pressure, and openly.

Data credibility analysis is achieved through five stages by looking at five aspects. They are (behavior, knowledge, artefacts, verbal messages, and values) and placing on the validity of data representations, examining researcher interventions to eliminate bias, assigning weights to evidence, comparative analysis, and negative case analysis. In the final stage, data that has gone through the previous stage is analyzed in the context of domain analysis (comprehensive picture), taxonomic analysis (details towards internal structure), componential analysis (characterization and specifications to understand contrasts between elements), and cultural theme analysis (searching for relationships and linkages between domains).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Built a culture in school and its change

The development of the education system through a cultural approach is a strategy implemented in the form of building synergy between school elements (principals, teachers, staff/educational staff) to improve the quality of the school learning process [26]. Each element of the school has a role in the passage of the cultural approach. The principal is a leader who plays a role in issuing policies and strategic decisions. Price [27] states that the principal is a "director" who can play the game's rhythm, direction, and tempo. In this case, the principal can change cultures, such as eliminating habits deemed inappropriate (harmful), not under social rules/norms, irrelevant to the times, and not following the school's vision and mission to make radical changes to school progress. Principals also have a substantial role in increasing the productivity of school elements through teacher development, strengthening organizational and interpersonal relationships in the school environment, and preventing open conflicts between elements in schools [28]–[30].

Although using a cultural approach to develop educational elements, it is undeniable that the structural approach initiated a cultural pattern which is a strategy in school development in the three objects of study. The development of culture at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta has been carried out since it was designated as an exemplary high school by the Government of the Republic of Indonesia as an exemplary high school, which in 1995 was appointed as a superior school by the Ministry of Education and Culture of Special Region of Yogyakarta and was perfected as a high school with an insight of excellence in 2008. This determination then made the principal the highest official in making decisions to determine attitudes that resulted in several achievements, namely the appointment of SMAN 1 Yogyakarta as the first school in Indonesia in 2004/2005 as the "Cambridge Centre", the occurrence of graduation scores above the national average, the high number of students with a continuing level of university. Success in achieving quality through a cultural approach is achieved by having qualified educators and supporting infrastructure. At SMAN 1 Yogyakarta, 64 teachers are the technical implementers of the principal's policies and learning facilitators for students, of which 95% have undergraduate education, and the rest are master's graduates. For infrastructure support facilities, SMAN 1 Yogyakarta has been supported by classrooms, physics, chemistry, language biology, and computer laboratories, multimedia rooms, internet rooms, libraries, student activity rooms, courtrooms, music rooms, and school's health clinic (UKS), as well as guidance and counselling.

The principal at SMAN 2 Yogyakarta has a vision of realizing a superior and leading school in providing education and teaching to produce graduates who have God-consciousness and faith (IMTAQ), morals, and master science and technology in a globalized world. There are 56 teaching staff at SMAN 2 Yogyakarta, with most having bachelor's and master's degrees. For infrastructure support facilities, SMAN 2 Yogyakarta has been supported by the presence of classrooms, libraries, student activity rooms, offices of intra-school student organizations (OSIS), cooperatives, halls, counseling guidance (BP/BK), teacher rooms, rooms having physics, chemistry, biology laboratories, informatics engineering, computers, languages, audio visual aids (AVA), educational media space. During the learning process, the teacher at SMAN 2 Yogyakarta acts as a technical implementer and plays a role in supporting the principal's vision by carrying out community service-based activities (including partnerships with the community and related institutions), building a conducive school culture in the form of values (discipline, hard work). Furthermore, intelligent, high spirit, want to move forward and confident, forward-oriented, quality-oriented, synergy work, democratic, togetherness, honesty, openness, clean culture, pleasant inner atmosphere and developing academic atmosphere and learning society), has the principle of professionalism, open to the development of technology and information, to develop democratic internal learning methods.

At SMAN 3 Yogyakarta, one of the efforts that the principal is concerned about is strengthening school engagement with alum networks for school development and supporting the vision of global insight. Learning at SMAN 3 is supported by the presence of 121 teachers with diplomas and bachelor's degrees and eight teachers with master's degrees. The state of the infrastructure of SMAN 3 is equipped with green land that is conducive to the learning process, study rooms, whiteboard and overhead projector media, multimedia learning rooms, laboratories (physics, biology, chemistry, language, computers, and the internet). In the aspect of talent and student interest in sports, the school is supported by the existence of basketball courts, badminton, tennis courts, gymnastics wards, table tennis, and other sports infrastructure.

Teachers have a very urgent role in improving the quality of education, especially for students, in creating cultural change in schools, including in the province of the special region of Yogyakarta, as the object of research studies. Nevertheless, unfortunately, at certain moments, teachers must face the pressure of structural policies that must be implemented but are not following the contextual conditions and are contrary to the mission of cultural change that has been built. The researcher's findings are that when the school is set as a role model, then certain limits or standards must be achieved by students (quality standards for school institutions, national examination standards for students, curriculum standards set, standards for infrastructure facilities to be established as institutions, and education with a particular reputation). Researchers see this as a form of paradox, where when these standards are applied, there will be problems even in an advanced

educational environment with the resources of teachers with good reputations, even though structural traps. This puts teachers in a dilemma when thinking and building a culture of progress in the school environment but trapped in the prevailing structural system environment [31]. In this case, it is challenging when teachers must adjust and even improve the culture that has been built. As a consequence, whether we realize it or not, teachers must place the cultural context far beyond the standards and various structural concepts and create certain competitive advantages through repetition of continuous learning practices, intensive mentoring between teachers and students in professional and capacity development, digital competence, global trends, and peer collaboration [32]–[36]. In the object of research, the researcher sees that the concept is implemented through school strategies such as providing many choices of specialization in extracurricular or extracurricular programs for students, teacher quality improvement programs, providing counselling/clinical services for students, providing multimedia laboratory facilities to increasing student capacity and teachers, student participation in international Olympiads that require teachers to develop further their competencies, as well as inter-regional teacher meetings to discuss developments in education and learning trends in the special region of Yogyakarta Province.

Infrastructure plays an essential role in supporting students and teachers' learning activities and experiences while in and developing themselves outside of school. The planning design and the results of infrastructure procurement affect the fulfilment of more specific learning needs, learning outcomes, to planning for future human resource investments [37]. In the research area, this condition is proven through the various student achievements in regional championships, national championships, and international science olympiad championships, which, apart from competency development, are also obtained through the support of science laboratory facilities that have been built to facilitate students' extracurricular activities. In addition, the achievements of inter-school sports championships were also obtained, one of which was the impact of the existence of training support facilities for students during extracurricular activities.

3.2. Mapping the dimensions of cultural approach in practices and the quality of learning activity

Spradley [23] formulated that the cultural approach in the learning process in schools is described through the development of cultures of behavior (behavior culture), knowledge (knowledge culture), and artefacts (artefacts culture). As a form of affirmation, Sergiovanni [24] states that cultural development has an impact on the progress and quality of schools, given the orientation of human factors, values and beliefs to the acceptance of the existence of multicultural situations. The development of these cultures has been implemented at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta, SMAN 2 Yogyakarta, and SMAN 3 Yogyakarta. It has become a link regarding the concept of a cultural approach to the impact of progress and school quality on school elements through the practice or existence of these elements.

3.2.1. Behavior culture

The results of the field study show that there are four important things that have a good impact on the success of school management and the behavior culture learning process. Some of these aspects include school principals, teachers, students, and education staff which are described and explained in Figure 1. Principals play a significant role in teacher professional development in several contexts, including providing instruction and direction, creating a learning environment, designing, and disseminating professional learning content and development, to assessing efforts to develop learning professionalism [38]. Based on these indications, the principal does not only function in the managerial process in schools but also relates directly and substantively to creating cultural learning, to increase teachers' capacity in schools through mutual understanding and trust between principals and teachers [39]. In the research area, the efforts made by school principals include, among others, high motivation to develop school capacity; the principal directly encourages the improvement of discipline in all elements of the school through regular joint deliberation. In addition, the principal seeks to encourage the improvement of technical capabilities, provision of facilities to support learning activities, the managerial capacity of teachers to students, to the capacity of positive values created by teachers to students. Basically, the principal's role is to make teachers continue to develop cognitively, affectively, or psychomotor. The contrast lies in the autonomy and ability to make strategic decisions in schools and facilitation between teachers in schools which are only owned by the principal so that the principal acts as the center of interaction between elements in the school.

As an element that plays a role in translating the results of decisions with the principal, the teacher is an element who interacts technically and directly with students in capacity building through a developed cultural approach. This is because the teacher understands the comprehensiveness of student needs in the learning process and is the element that best understands how to overcome learning obstacles for students, so high-capacity teachers are needed to make cultural learning run optimally [40]. In addition to having a formal reputation in the form of teacher education levels and many teachers, teachers also implement democratic learning activities, set themselves as role models of discipline, instill social awareness and religiosity in

students, stimulate students to actively discuss as well as facilitators, mastery of the material, map students' interests and talents, open learning services openly. To increase their competency capacity, teachers always develop networks between teachers outside of school, develop themselves in positive interests, increase the encouragement of collaboration between students, conduct learning-based research about schools and discuss problems or challenges faced to be solved together.

Figure 1. Four elements of school in strengthening behavioral culture

The learning culture by the teacher is then directed at learning processes for students to carry out various activities that produce positive values in learning development. A learning system from the teacher will have the opportunity to bridge the material and the teacher's teaching patterns to the final results of learning by students through positive values [41]. In other words, students have a chance of success when they apply linearly the input obtained from the teacher. The learning process applied by teachers in the research area can be seen from the results of the achievements, which then form patterns for students in the form of voluntary collaborative learning habits, performing religious rituals during break hours, getting used to positive activities at school and being disciplined in protecting the environment, having an excellent physical appearance, simple, maintaining good relations with teachers and school elements, maintaining ethics and quality of discipline to school rules, developing personal interests and talents independently, participating in positive programs provided by the school voluntarily.

School learning support staff, in addition to overseeing administration, also support the activities of principals and teachers and provide services to students regarding the needs of learning facilities. The involvement of support staff plays a role in improving learning conduciveness, encouraging collaboration between school elements, especially teachers, student learning participation patterns, and controlling learning classes [42], [43]. The practice of administrative staff and learning support is carried out through administrative roles, managing libraries, and serving in laboratory management following regulations, especially in providing services to students and teachers who support the process of developing a learning culture. Indirectly, the role of these staff for school principals will help achieve the vision targets set through service management and use of strategic assets in schools, and for teachers, it will facilitate learning control and assistance for students who require independent learning access with the expected acceleration. In addition, one of the administrative roles is in the form of data collection to assist in decision-making in evaluating learning.

3.2.2. Knowledge culture

Spradley [23] defines knowledge culture as "what is known" by someone during the learning process. At the level of reality, knowledge is an important part that is often hidden and not revealed openly, so it requires disclosure to see the extent to which the processes and results of the culture of knowledge in learning in schools are. The quality of learning is a variable that can be used as a measuring tool in assessing how a cultural approach has been applied in schools and assessing the effectiveness of the approach contextually. In the study of Loh and Teo [44], the identification of educational culture applied in Asia shows that basically, the learning culture in Indonesia has similarities with Singapore, Hong Kong, South Korea, and Malaysia with the results of identifying similarities in the collectivity aspect, hierarchy, masculinity, avoid uncertainty, and have a long-term view. More technically, it is explained that several countries that have similarities with Indonesia practice teacher-centered and tiered learning styles (which tend to be hierarchical), the teacher becomes a facilitator who describes the material and direction of learning so that it is more detailed in terms of content and context, the existence of etiquette behaviors. Furthermore, minimal post-learning questions, focusing on aspects of personal relationships, implicit and often indirect communication, the structural approach is widely used (one of the pieces of evidence relates to the existence of applied national standards), success is measured by academic performance. It is a matter of pride and the selection of learning materials based on career goals and aspirations [44]. This context is conveyed in Figure 2 which explains the school program, the impacts, and the best targets to be achieved.

Figure 2. Programs, impacts, and achievement targets through the knowledge culture scheme

Disclosure of the culture of knowledge through program learning in schools is applied through extracurricular programs that support academic success for students. The teachers implemented an increased role of facilitator in the form of team teach mentoring, reduced formal study hours to a maximum of two hours/day, mental preparation and technical skills, repetition of exams through tryouts, deepening of learning materials, practicum, remedial, clinical services, development of artistic creativity. Culture and language, and facilitation of the readiness for the implementation of the science olympiad. Extracurricular programs, in addition to supporting students' academics, also aim to assist students in passing the national exam as the final graduation standard of the school.

Another culture of knowledge is through intra-curricular activities at school. This activity has academic benefits for several programs related to the field of learning. Nevertheless, on the other hand, extracurricular activities support students' future soft skills and investment in human resources. Some extracurricular programs include youth science club or KIR, spirituality, journalism, theatre, boy scout activities, foreign language clubs, cooperatives, computers, and school security guards. In sports such as martial art, basketball, vocal group, young Indonesia red cross, taekwondo, philately, band/music, nature lovers, choir, table tennis, football, and volleyball. In the field of community service through inculcating exemplary images, exemplary devotional camps and fostered villages, implementation of 7K (7 programs so that students have good habits), student-teacher relationships, flag ceremonies, provision of computer skills, and student exchange.

3.2.3. Artifacts culture

Learning in Indonesia is carried out through a structural approach, with the logical consequences of general policies and technical guidelines being the primary foundation of learning. However, artefact culture is the key to assessing the school's reputation and internal development motivation to develop themselves and excel in all fields according to their interests and talents. Gottsmann, Trohel, and Petitfaux [45] identified that artefacts provide a symbolic meaning of knowledge built by teachers about learning culture and proof of an ongoing reputation. There are three meanings built by Gottsmann, Trohel, and Petitfaux [45] related to artefacts, among others: first, the meaning of the exchange of quality improvement between teachers and students through symbolic artefacts (to calculate scores) and the development of various student perceptions; second, the meaning of "service quality improvement", by using material artefacts to help develop good school services, and; third, refers to the unexpected knowledge by the teacher of the student's capacity.

The meaning of artefacts in the research area is built to support building a learning culture and increase students' competence in contextual interests and talents. The meaning of improving the quality of students is realized through a symbolic form in the form of documenting data on student entrance exam results. The symbolic for teachers and schools, this meaning then becomes an achievement of pride and an assessment of teacher competence so that it continues to encourage to cultivate a symbolic achievement of student learning outcomes. It is known that the average number of schools is above the set standard in the research area. In addition, in the field of study, various championships were also achieved through trophies, medals, and certificates of appreciation by students or schools in regional, national, and international olympic championships. This meaning also plays a role in supporting the principal's vision so that it becomes a benchmark for the quality of the principal's Leadership as the implementing center and facilitator in learning, whether it can maintain a quality culture, improve, or vice versa.

The following meaning relates to the existence of material artefacts to create service quality and develop a better learning situation. This relates to the school's infrastructure, equipment, methods, or materials, which ultimately shows the extent to which learning facilitation services show their superiority in accommodating learning interests and investment in human resources. Various material artefacts are held on research objects, such as regional environmental infrastructure that supports security (restrictions on access in

and out of the school environment), comfort (green environment), and student enthusiasm in the implementation of learning (science/technology/social science laboratory facilities, sports, art spaces, multimedia, worship, mental/psychic consultation, library). These artefacts refer to the needs of students and teachers to support learning and create contextual advantages based on their interests and talents. This simultaneously facilitates capacities that may be beyond prediction, which will later assist students in optimizing expectations and perceptions of the feasibility of the school.

The last meaning in the form of artefacts refers to “unexpected knowledge” by the teacher of the student’s capacity. The existence of evidence of awards in the form of trophies, medals, and certificates of awards at international, national, or regional championships is proof of student capacity. Nevertheless, what is unexpected is when the artefact becomes a form of appreciation that the teacher does not master, or even the capacity of students exceeds that of other students or teachers in a particular field of interest. Some students may not master the capacity in academics and tend to be on the standard line of ability, but in certain areas having expertise far above the average of most students brings a particular pride. The process of cultural approach that must be built is to continue to give awards and strengthen these areas of expertise. In the short term, there will be an assumption that these skills are not affiliated with academic learning. However, in the long term, the documentation of tracer study data for school alums implemented by the school will encourage pride and increase confidence in the quality of schools in practicing cultural learning.

3.3. Analysis of value implementation through behavioral culture, knowledge, and artifacts

The implementation and practice of various programs, policies, and habits formed in a learning culture in schools have produced specific values. Values are formed into abstract meanings but become norms trusted and able to appear as a form of learning outcomes obtained. It is essential to understand the value given the significance of the changes that occur in students [46]. In addition, values also have a more significant role than pedagogical during learning on the basis of “meaning in learning pedagogy” [46].

The value classification analysis of cultural learning has resulted in a synthesis of the culture of behavior (behavior culture), knowledge (knowledge culture), and artefacts (artefact culture). From all school elements, both at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta, SMAN 2 Yogyakarta, and SMAN 3 Yogyakarta, there are 12 grades for learning practices. 12 These values are applied for a specific purpose and give meaning to why it is essential to apply. Through the observation model in the school environment and interviews with school elements, 12 values were found, proven through various activities related to behavior, knowledge, and artefacts in the research area. The description of the 12 values is described in Table 1.

Table 1 is the result of the synthesis of the implementation of values that have been applied in SMAN 1 Yogyakarta, SMAN 2 Yogyakarta, and SMAN 3 Yogyakarta, which departs from the synthesis of cultural behavior, knowledge, and artefacts expressed by Spradley [23]. Behavioral practices, learning, and symbolic evidence within and outside the school become a kind of evidence studied by researchers, each of which gives meaning to the extent to which schools apply culturally based values to develop schools.

The synthesis of 12 values in the scope of the research area in the province of the special region of Yogyakarta can be an alternative to several previous studies. In other words, this study confirms studies that become references, such as the poor structural development system as revealed by Sari [3], the quality gap between schools and the lack of policies to improve the quality of education facilitation [6], [7]. Mechanisms for measuring improvements in teacher performance are related to student output which is not significant [9], not yet optimal contextuality of curriculum implementation in schools [10], quality constraints and commitment of technical implementers (teachers), education administrators, and participation of parents. bad [11]. Several aspects of cultural learning strategies which are then described as values and practices, can be an alternative solution to the problem gap. Building a structured learning approach that looks solid is fragile at the technical level of application. The practices and values that emerged in this study could become a reference for correcting various contextual problems or bridging the gap in the reference study.

On the other hand, this study has limited implications in the context of a structural approach in the form of macro problems such as disparities in access to education between regions [4], expansion of access to education which is constrained by a political agenda, budget constraints, mechanisms, and the lack of appreciation of awards [5], the calculation of the wrong value of budgeting so that it is not comparable to improving the quality of education [8], to corruption which has a destructive impact on education sector spending in several regions in Indonesia [12]. This is based on a research area that is limited to the internal scope of schools and the application of technical policies by synthesizing strategies to overcome structural-based learning techniques. In other words, the synthesis of this study has difficulty overcoming the problem gaps in these studies based on the limitation of the research domain and the scope of authority that is only limited to internal schools.

Table 1. Values, practices, goals/meanings, and resources

Value	Practice and goals/meanings		Resources
	Practice	Goals/meanings	
Religiosity and tolerance	Application of worship according to individual beliefs; Not being racist (in religion)	Creating a learning area based on religious norms	School day-to-day observations; The school's vision-mission; school rules and regulations
Fairness	Appropriate action in the exam; No theft cases	Improve school safety and trust between school elements	Observation of the counselling room about school cases; Interview with students
Openness	The principal opens a pattern of participation for school elements; Teachers are not anti-criticism in learning; Students often ask openly in discussions or express opinions	Open up opportunities for new ideas and experiences; practice openness, democracy, and anti-criticism on the attitudes/opinions of others	Principal and teacher interviews; Observation of class activities
Unyielding	High enthusiasm of students in learning and obeying school rules; Principals and teachers continue to facilitate students' abilities	Strengthening students' mentality so that they continue to improve their abilities; Principals and teachers train themselves to be motivators in student progress	Principal, teacher, and student interviews; Observation of development programs, relationships between school elements, and actions of school elements
Learner mentality, critical, logical, and rational	Collaboration and discussion of learning between students and teachers; Intensive study visits to the library; facilitating student interest in various programs	Improving the knowledge and expertise of school elements in depth	School reputation data (including teachers and students); Literature (library) visit data; championship artefact observation
Awareness improves the quality of learning	Comparative studies between institutions; Discussion and evaluation of learning; ranking as evaluation; collaboration increases learning capacity	Increase awareness and responsibility for the importance of improving self-quality and encourage each other to develop	Principal, teacher, and student interviews; Observation of development and evidence of institutional visit artefacts
Mutual respect	Applying politeness following the traditions of eastern society; Fair play action in school sports competitions	Caring for harmony and social ties between school elements	Principal, teacher, and student interviews; Observation of the counselling room on school cases; observation of artefacts of school rules/regulations
Unity	Avoiding ethnic and regional racist activities (primordialism); Service and social program collaboration; avoid open conflicts and resolve them behind closed doors in case of conflict	Prevent/reduce conflicts that hurt the learning process	Principal, teacher, and student interviews; Observation of the counselling room on school cases
Positive think and act	Be humble and positive in peer association; Avoid temperamental attitudes and get used to capturing complete and objective information; Avoid prejudice in learning activities such as competing for test scores	Avoid superficial thinking and prejudice; Become a role model in positive thoughts/attitudes among peers	Principal, teacher, and student interviews; Observation of the counselling room about the characteristics of the school and student association patterns
Discipline	Carry out each series of learning activities according to the appropriate time, even though there are still a few students who are late in the series; Obey school rules; orderly and regularly carry out the agreed obligations (picket)	Get used to learning activities regularly, systematically, and consistently	Observation of class activities and school rules/rules
Responsibility	Obey the agreements that have been drawn up together, such as class rules, doing group work in a distributed manner, and completing school assignments	Instill a pattern of responsibility and complete work ideally	Observation of class activities and student learning
Collectivity	Collaborative problem-solving learning; Social service activities; provide support in competitions, learning activities, and so on	Increase social values and harmony between school elements	Observation of activities, daily activities, and student learning

4. CONCLUSION

The results showed that the quality of learning in the research area (SMAN 1 Yogyakarta, SMAN 2 Yogyakarta, and SMAN 3 Yogyakarta) was not purely based on the demands of a structured learning approach strategy implemented by the government. The strategy is based on value-based and practice-based development efforts, which are then applied to learning cultures (behaviors, knowledge, and artefacts) and incorporated into a learning culture development pattern and a gradual change pattern. The implication of this study is the concept of developing a cultural learning strategy while implementing structural policies by the government. However, for several studies that have not been confirmed (a limitation of this research study), further studies are needed on a study pattern with a broader scope related to structural education problems that are still difficult to overcome.

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